

TOWARDS SUSTAINABILITY IN EDUCATION: LESSONS FROM THE FEE ECO-SCHOOLS PROGRAM IN QATAR

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Ruba Hinnawi, Seda Duygu Sever-Mehmetoğlu ,
Özcan Öztürk, and Evren Tok

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College of Public Policy

جامعة حمد بن خليفة
HAMAD BIN KHALIFA UNIVERSITY

TOWARDS SUSTAINABILITY IN EDUCATION: LESSONS FROM THE FEE ECO-SCHOOLS PROGRAM IN QATAR

Editors:

Ruba Hinnawi

Technical Lead
Earthna

Dr. Seda Duygu Sever-Mehmetoğlu

Post-Doctoral Research Associate
Carnegie Mellon University in Qatar

Dr. Özcan Öztürk

Assistant Professor
Hamad Bin Khalifa University

Dr. Evren Tok

Associate Professor
Hamad Bin Khalifa University

Design:

Irshad Ibrahim

Research Assistant
Hamad Bin Khalifa University

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1. Introduction:

The Qatar National Vision 2030 (QNV 2030) recognizes the importance of sustainable development, emphasizing the need to preserve and protect the environment—including its air, land, water, and biological diversity—and to cultivate an environmentally conscious populace. It sets forth ambitious goals within its educational strategy to bolster environmental awareness, promote practices of sustainable production and consumption, and foster behaviors supportive of environmental sustainability, such as the responsible use of water and electricity.

The development of educational curricula and training programs tailored to Qatar's present and future needs has gained increasing recognition from governmental authorities. These efforts, combined with supportive policies and public resources, are pivotal in advancing sustainability and social progress. This includes enhancing environmental education in schools, integrating sustainability principles into the curriculum, and forging connections between local and global educational initiatives.

Qatar's political commitment to incorporating sustainable development into its educational curriculum is evident, supported by a broad array of stakeholders working to weave education for sustainable development (ESD) into teaching and learning practices. This includes the creation of educational tools designed to immerse students in practical sustainability experiences that address critical local concerns. The nation's ESD landscape features a rich tapestry of initiatives, projects, and contributors from both formal and informal sectors, all playing a role in advancing ESD through their respective activities and partnerships. However, these programs and initiatives manifest through a variety of channels, diverse and often uncoordinated, spanning both formal and informal education spheres.

From pre-primary to secondary schools, Qatar hosts 318 public schools with more than 126,000 students, and more than 686 private schools serving approximately 200,000 students of mixed

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nationality.¹ The schools differ from each other by nationalities, curriculum and by their practices in education for sustainable development. Due to changes in the student demographics, teacher profiles, physical, and financial resources across different schools, some efforts for ESD remain as extracurricular, and / or ad-hoc activities which cannot be scaled to the entire education system. This underlines the need to have a systematic, long-term, flexible tool that can be adopted by the diverse school and student profiles.

The Foundation for Environmental Education Eco-Schools program stands out as a good practice to address this need. The FEE Eco-Schools program is a unique program that provides a systematic long-term approach to sustainable change at school grounds at all levels. It brings schools operational efficiency and climate change education together with action-based learning opportunities.

This report offers a comprehensive look at how the FEE Eco-School Program is situated within the Qatari context in education for sustainable development and investigates its impact on the enrolled schools' educational system and students' learning outcomes. Regarding the reflections from the FEE Eco-Schools, the report represents insights concerning the experience of teachers who have taken up the FEE Eco-Schools program. These insights draw upon a survey collecting feedback from schools within Qatar who have signed up to the FEE Eco-Schools program, conducted by Earthna. Earthna, formerly known as Qatar Green Building Council, is the national operator for the FEE Eco-Schools program in Qatar since 2018.

¹ Ministry of Education and Higher Education. (2022). *Annual Statistics of Education in the State of Qatar*. [https://www.edu.gov.qa/Documents/HigherEdTracks/Annual%20Statistics%202020-2021_%20معتد\[2083\].pdf](https://www.edu.gov.qa/Documents/HigherEdTracks/Annual%20Statistics%202020-2021_%20معتد[2083].pdf).

2. FEE Eco-Schools program supporting Quality Education

From its modest beginnings in 1994 in a few European countries, the FEE Eco-Schools program has expanded to effect positive climate change in some forty-eight seven hundred schools in seventy-three countries by FEE member organizations and twenty-six countries through international schools as per the year 2023. The impact of the program is well recognized and respected by stakeholders that range from United Nations (UN) agencies to the communities in which a school is ingrained.

FEE Eco-Schools students are truly inspirational in what they do and set examples for everyone to follow. The FEE Eco-Schools program is recognised globally as a world leader within the fields of Environmental Education (EE) and Education for Sustainable Development (ESD).

The FEE Eco-Schools program is not just an economic model that focuses on operational efficiency to lower costs, it is a student-led model that places the students at the centre of a process of change towards sustainability. Moreover, the program allows for creating stakeholder partnerships to connect the students to the real-world sustainability related challenges in their communities. The experiences gained from the FEE Eco-Schools program show that the program draws its strength from how it engages young people and how their work draws others to engage in positive action in their own communities and wider for positive climate change.

What distinguishes the FEE Eco-Schools program from other initiatives is the international framework, which allows the schools from different countries to collaborate on the same level tackling twelve themes. The FEE Eco-Schools program engages young people in positive action projects in their school and community through the transformative Seven- Step methodology framework to acquire valuable skills in problem-solving. The seven steps of the FEE Eco-Schools program and 12 themes addressed as per the program are detailed in Figures.

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Figure 1. The seven steps of the FEE Eco-Schools program and 12 Themes

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The purpose of the FEE Eco-Schools program is to encourage the students to act for sustainability and to equip them to be changemakers in their communities and workplaces. This proactive approach empowers the students as active citizens capable of taking responsible action for the planet.

The FEE Eco-schools program was recognized recently by the UNESCO global initiative: Greening Education Partnership, as a program that meets the GEP criteria and accredited as a whole school approach. The GEP is structured around four key pillars of transformative education: greening schools, greening curriculum, greening teachers training and greening communities. The initiative sets a target for all countries to adapt a green school accreditation scheme in at least 50% of schools, colleges and universities by 2030. Therefore, the FEE Eco-schools program offers countries and Qatar a tool to meet the international commitment to achieve the ESD and the SDGs.

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Globally, the FEE Eco-Schools program network has created many channels within government educational institutes and authorities to propose and endorse many learning forms, to support the learning transformative agenda towards sustainable and resilient communities. The educational models are changing both locally and at an international level, becoming more hands-on. The

schools that are involved in the FEE Eco-Schools program are provided with tools to adapt and understand the new goals and methods for ESD, as they follow very similar principles, including but not limited to, collaboration, teamwork, learning by doing, project-based learning, problem solving, critical thinking, real-world experiences.

3. FEE Eco-Schools program in Qatar

As the national operator of the FEE Eco-Schools program, Earthna acknowledges the profound impact of education in steering the Qatari community towards greater sustainability. Earthna advocates for the integration of the FEE Eco-Schools program with place-based environmental education as a pivotal strategy to nurture future generations with a sustainability mindset. By connecting students with their immediate surroundings, we cultivate a sense of belonging, thereby linking their learning to environmental ethics and values. This approach is crucial for fostering behavioral change and driving impactful actions towards sustainable development.

In 2023, Qatar boasted 48 schools registered under the FEE Eco-School program, including 14 that were honored with the Green Flag Award, involving over 30,600 students and more than 5,730 teachers and support staff. The program benefits from collaborations with both national and international strategic partners, significantly enhancing the educational experience for students and teachers and promoting a sense of global citizenship. Partners such as Tarsheed-Kahramaa, the Quranic Botanic Gardens, the Supreme Committee for Delivery and Legacy, Qatar Foundation, and the international network of the FEE Eco-Schools program exemplify these enriching partnerships and affiliations.

3.1 Teacher Reflections on FEE Eco-Schools Experience

The survey conducted by Earthna is based on a feedback questionnaire distributed to the FEE Eco-Schools' community in Qatar, with the purpose of collecting information about the program's strength, opportunities, and student's learning outcomes. The survey addressed teachers and school staff

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members at the FEE Eco-Schools to capture their experience with the program as well as their reflections on the perceived impact of the program on environmental literacy, and student engagement.

The survey was sent out to thirty-one schools and fifty-six responses were received. The survey included questions about the integration of environmental literacy in the curriculum, its impact on students learning outcomes. As well as the FEE Eco-Schools program implementation and school engagement, where educators had the chance to share their challenges and best practices.

The experience of teachers in their FEE Eco-Schools journey is extremely insightful in understanding what makes the FEE Eco-Schools program different than any other initiatives or projects which focus on similar issue areas. As stated by 20.75% of teachers responding to the survey, the FEE Eco-Schools program guide schools on how to systematically drive real sustainable change for real impact in schools. Collectively, the Seven- Step methodology (see earlier infographic depicting the seven steps), the sustainability of the program as the green flag award needs to be renewed every two years and the tools and educational resources offered by the program's network, grant a long term and sustainable change in schools (Figure 2).

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As illustrated in **Figure 3**, 89% of the teachers believe that in the FEE Eco-Schools program, environmental education is significantly integrated into the curriculum and/or is covered as a separate subject.

As per the survey results, the teachers also agree (28%) and strongly agree (72%) that one of the learning outcomes of integrating environmental education in the curriculum, is to increase students' knowledge about earth, life, and ecosystems. The FEE Eco-Schools program meets the "Link to Curriculum" step to fulfil the Green Flag requirements. According to their experience, the teachers strongly agree (59%) and agree (37%), [a total of 97%], that when environmental education is embedded into the curriculum, it enhances students' appreciation and respect to nature, values, as well as their motivation and intention to act responsibly.

Figure 4, shows that the majority of the teachers in the sample think that a curriculum which incorporates environmental education, increases students' competencies and skills, such as analysis, investigation, action plan developments. This contributes to a positive behaviour of the students towards climate change.

Figure 5: 93% of the respondents indicate that integrating environmental education into the curriculum increases students' responsible behaviour that leads to practice and positive action for climate change.

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Beyond environmental education, the FEE Eco-Schools program provides a holistic approach to teaching and learning that integrates the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), local culture, and values into the educational experience. A significant advantage of the FEE Eco-Schools program is its ability to foster a deeper connection with the SDGs. According to responses from teachers participating in the survey, a majority of their activities are designed to align with the SDGs, as illustrated in Figure 6.

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Most of the participants indicate that culture, values, and place have strong resonance in the FEE Eco-Schools program (Figure 7). However, the local understanding of environment and the way they are embedded into the curriculum requires further investigation.

Figure 8 reveals that 79% of the teachers surveyed either agree or strongly agree that the FEE Eco-Schools program exemplifies global citizenship through its international network. The qualitative insights from teachers closely align with the competencies, knowledge, and skills associated with the concept of "global citizenship." According to UNESCO's definition, education should aim to empower students of all ages to comprehend both local and global issues, encouraging them to become proactive agents of change toward more peaceful, inclusive, tolerant, and sustainable societies.²

The feedback from teachers reveals a substantial commitment to preparing the students to become responsible global citizens. To illustrate, a point commonly raised by the teachers concerns the global interactions within the FEE Eco-Schools program. Teachers reflect that even travelling to other countries can provide the students invaluable experiences through interaction with other cultures. The FEE Eco-Schools program related activities are also reported to connect the students internationally with their peers and with the global community through best practice sharing or

² Unesco. 2022. Global Citizenship Education. <https://en.unesco.org/themes/gced>.

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global events and campaigns initiated by FEE Eco-Schools internationally such as the GAIA 20:30 Global Action Days Campaign.

Based on the feedback from teachers, the FEE Eco-Schools program illustrates to students how local lifestyles can have a global impact, inspiring them to adopt a "think globally, act locally" approach. The program emphasizes linking local actions to global implications, fostering a sense of planetary stewardship and connection to the global community through its projects, initiatives, and events.

Teachers highlight the importance of taking responsibility, showcasing the FEE Eco-Schools program's commitment to not only educating students about global issues but also involving their families and communities as a crucial step in the program's Seven-Step methodology. This approach extends learning beyond the classroom, encouraging students and school staff to adopt sustainable lifestyle changes. These include practices such as composting at home, pursuing a zero-waste lifestyle, recycling, consuming water responsibly, and raising awareness about global warming across various platforms.

Illustration 1: 12 Themes of Eco Schools Program

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Among the themes waste, litter and food waste stands out with 28.6% as the most addressed topics in the schools in Qatar. The projects in this theme specifically aimed at teaching students to reduce, reuse, and recycle, composting organic waste, and upcycling plastic and glass waste.

Overall, the teachers who responded to the survey, reported more than 160 projects, action items or initiatives which tackle various themes (Figure 9) in their schools' greening journey in Qatar.

To highlight waste management best practices, a significant number of FEE Eco-Schools in Qatar have implemented "Good On One Side" (GOOS) trays in each classroom and near printing stations to minimize paper use. Moreover, all these schools have adopted a policy against single-use plastic water bottles, showcasing the students' growing awareness of the need to rethink consumption habits.

In one school, students and staff collect recyclable materials like bottles, jars, and cardboard boxes, repurposing them into both functional and aesthetically pleasing utensils, or utilizing them to create original art pieces. Another school engages its students in monitoring food waste by weighing leftovers after snack times and lunch breaks for each class, followed by graphing the data daily. This practice has sparked interest among students, staff, and the wider community in waste reduction, with an increasing number of students taking the initiative to ensure their waste is properly disposed of in the designated buckets.

Themes such as climate change, global citizenship, biodiversity, and nature are also fervently explored by the schools. Projects like the "Forest School," Herbal Gardens, artificial ponds, and greenhouses for fruit and vegetable cultivation are common. Notably, the theme of "Marine and Coast" receives comparatively less attention, which is intriguing given Qatar's vulnerability in terms of its marine ecosystems.

3.2 Areas for Future Progress

To highlight waste management best practices, the majority of FEE Eco-Schools in Qatar have implemented "Good On One Side" (GOOS) trays in each classroom and near printing stations to minimize paper use. Furthermore, all participating schools have adopted policies to become "single-use plastic water bottle free," demonstrating to students the importance of rethinking consumption habits.

Themes such as climate change, global citizenship, biodiversity, and nature are also actively pursued by the schools. Initiatives like

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the Forest School project, herbal gardens, artificial ponds, and greenhouses for fruit and vegetable cultivation are commonly adopted. Interestingly, despite Qatar's vulnerabilities concerning marine ecosystems, the theme of "Marine and Coast" is among the least addressed.

Despite the FEE Eco-Schools program's positive contributions and its recognized impact on learning outcomes, the survey highlighted areas needing improvement for the future. One such area is the integration of environmental education into community-level practices. A significant number of teachers noted a disconnect between the knowledge and practices experienced on school grounds versus those outside school (Figure 10). Almost all teachers concurred (65% strongly agree, 35% agree) that creating partnerships to extend students' learning experiences beyond school premises and providing practical opportunities for positive behavioural change could be an effective solution to this issue.

Another area of improvement concerns the operational management of schools. When it comes to the impact of the FEE Eco-Schools program on the operational management of the school, the survey results reveal that the answers are more varied as opposed to the strong agreement on positive educational outcomes (Figure 11).

There are differing answers among the teachers regarding how the FEE Eco-Schools program has been improving energy, water, or waste management in their schools. While some still agree that there has been some improvement, others indicate a neutral or even negative stand. This might be referred to the absence of monitoring and data collection, and coordination between the school's facility management, the school management, and the FEE Eco-Schools program committee.

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It is crucial to perceive the program as a tool to integrate sustainability policies and practices in the school management decision making process to achieve sustainability at both educational and operational levels. Such a holistic approach to integrate sustainability at all levels within the school ecosystem might be the main obstacle towards achieving the Green Flag Award. More than half of the registered schools in Qatar have not achieved the Green Flag Award (Figure 12). This indicates that there is still room for progress in the management side.

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The FEE Eco-Schools program allows the students to get connected with their peers in the international arena through the program's network and multiple international campaigns and competitions. Clear examples of these are the global FEE Eco-Schools projects such as Children for Children campaign and Litter Less. More than 77% of the teachers declared that they have participated in Biodiversity Global Action Days in 2021 and 2022. Moreover, 46.3% of the teachers stated that they are engaging in campaigns, competitions, projects and even events beyond the FEE Eco-Schools network (Figure 13).

However, it is also important to underline the results which show that, 43% of the teachers are not able to participate into a broader series of events outside the FEE Eco-Schools program network, due to several challenges. Apart from the disruptions caused by the global pandemic, some of these challenges include lack of organization, lack of communication and advertisement. Some teachers report that such events, competitions, or projects usually come with very late notice to offer enough time to the teachers and students to get prepared. A commonly stated reason also concerns the lack of capacity to support extra initiatives other than what their schools are already a part of.

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Overall, many of the teachers surveyed strongly agree (63%) or agree (30%) that FEE Eco-Schools program should be applied to all schools in Qatar (Figure 14).

The qualitative feedback from teachers regarding their support for the widespread adoption of the FEE Eco-Schools program across Qatari schools offers insightful conclusions. Academically, the program is praised for enhancing the experiential learning process, aiding students in developing their analytical and creative skills, and providing them with opportunities to lead and evaluate the impact of sustainable changes in their school environment.

The findings suggest that the FEE Eco-Schools program holds the potential to bring additional advantages to Qatari schools. Several educators highlight how the program's attributes could contribute to achieving the objectives of the Qatar National Vision 2030 by fostering a culture of sustainability and nurturing more responsible individuals and citizens. According to teacher feedback, expanding the FEE Eco-Schools network in Qatar could bolster efforts towards more proactive, localized actions addressing specific environmental challenges unique to Qatar, such as waste management, water security, and pollution control. This would be particularly effective if schools' initiatives were aligned and coordinated with national sustainability campaigns and environmental conservation projects.

3. Conclusions and Recommendations

Aligning with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) is identified as an effective method for teaching global citizenship in Qatar. The FEE Eco-Schools program, with its universal themes, connects students to both global citizenship and environmental stewardship. The program's seven-step methodology aids students and teachers in critically analyzing these themes, enabling active participation in their schools and communities.

Teachers' insights suggest that these components can equip Qatari youth with the knowledge and sense of responsibility necessary for fostering an eco-friendly and sustainable future. This approach raises awareness among students about global interdependencies, highlighting how their actions can significantly influence their ecological footprint.

Teachers' experiences indicate that to foster positive change in education for sustainable development, an integrated approach must be developed for educational institutions to support the FEE Eco-Schools program. Governmental bodies, academia, and both the private and public sectors are urged to assist schools on their journey to achieving the FEE Eco-Schools Green Flag Award.

Moreover, it is vital to develop tools to assess the effectiveness of this integrated framework, measuring behavioral change and performance indicators for the operational efficiency of the built environment. This proposed approach, based on the FEE Eco-Schools program, should rest on three fundamental pillars: 1) The FEE Eco-Schools program as a dynamic tool for action-based, goal-oriented, and structured activities aimed at integrating sustainability into schools; 2) Localized environmental literacy woven into the curriculum to connect students with their immediate surroundings; and 3) Enhancing educators' capacity to confidently and effectively teach about environmental challenges.

These pillars promise a learning experience that transcends the confines of the classroom, empowering students to think and act in harmony with their local context and interconnected ecosystems globally. Students should be furnished with the necessary skills

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and tools to contribute to nature's regeneration. This can be achieved by embedding education for sustainable development within the education system, rather than treating it as an additional subject or extracurricular activity.

The FEE Eco-Schools program integrates environment and nature seamlessly within its structure. Its seven-step methodology provides a distinctive experience that addresses the desired learning outcomes: environmental knowledge, awareness of one's role in relation to the environment, and the competency and behavior to initiate and lead positive change.

Furthermore, the program recognizes the crucial role of families and communities, who are integral to the school's eco-committee (Step 1). This underscores the value of collective social responsibility and offers students the chance to blend their education with everyday life. Activities within the FEE Eco-Schools foster connections between students and their physical surroundings, facilitating interactions that benefit both and all related ecosystems.

This report concludes that adopting and broadening the FEE Eco-Schools program through the national curriculum can assist Qatar in weaving education for sustainable development into its educational framework. Such an initiative can serve as a catalyst for Qatar to achieve its National Vision 2030, fulfill its global climate change commitments, and cultivate resilient communities.